

Situational Awareness for Maritime Surveillance

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Abstract— The identification and application of best practices for the integration of sensors to an existing NMSS (National Maritime Surveillance System) and the associated current needs of Command and Control (C2) require an enhanced Operator Situational Awareness with advanced Human-Machine Interface (HMI) technologies. This paper presents a maritime surveillance and control platform designed to provide enhanced situational awareness in order to overcome the limitations of the traditional methods (direct line of sight, coast radar, voice communication, etc) and to detect abnormal situations and activities differing from expected behaviors. The goal of this work is to analyze: (a) real fusion system applications required to operate on wide areas for long periods of time, (b) basic capabilities such as context adaptation and the resolution of fusion inconsistencies; for which online and zonal configuration capabilities and quality metrics of context adaptation have been designed and developed. This allows to use powerful or more specific configurations for localized scenarios (risks, hazards, clutter, anomalous behaviours, navigation alerts, weather anomalies).

Keywords—data fusion; context-aided fusion; maritime surveillance; C2; real time; decision-making; HMI, metrics.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Situational Awareness

The maritime services focus their priorities on efficient vessel transits with the best possible safe navigation, improving upon current operational procedures and tools for these services.

The general goal will always be to provide enhanced situational awareness in order to overcome the limitations of traditional methods (direct line of sight, coast radar, voice communication, etc) and to detect abnormal situations and activities which differs from expected behaviours.

Starting from the characterization and assessment on sources (raw or processed sensor data), and from the identification of potential use cases in the maritime domain, it is possible to determine the best approach to integrate these sources into existing multi-sensor network architectures [1], [4]. To do so, it is needed to perform a detailed modelling of the sensors, their interfaces and advanced fusion algorithms in order to establish the expected performance.

Fig. 1. Overview of the MSCS (Maritime Surveillance and Control System) Context [1]

On the other hand, these sensory data may not be enough to understand specific use cases and complex operational scenarios, requiring additional contextual information to model and build a successful description of the situation.

This is why contextual information can supply the supplementary knowledge to understand complex situations and to better predict how vessels behave [5], [7].

The main types of context information are:

- Navigation environment status: geographic knowledge of the coastline, currents, tides, bathymetry, weather, sea state and ice, etc.
- Navigation conditions: navigation regulations, IHO/IMO and IALA recommendations, ECDIS, etc.
- Target classification:
 - Type of objective: anti-pollution equipment, diving ship, fishing, cargo vessel (hazardous), high speed craft, naval ship, patrol ship, passenger ship, oil tanker, etc.
 - Navigational status: moored, aground, at anchor, abrupt manoeuvre, restricted manoeuvrability, in course, fishing, etc.
 - Risk / threat status: friend, assumed friend, hostile, suspect, neutral, unknown, pending.
- Performance of the detection sensors: cooperative or not, coverage, accuracy, resolution, refresh period, etc.
- Mission (Uses Cases).

B. HMI for Decision Making

The processed data are obtained from all the sources involved in real time and shared by a multi-sensor network. The resources for the execution of C2 operations use these data online and offline in order to address the cognitive ability in operations and the problem of information overload.

It is required a user-friendly and simple graphic HMI environment when taking manual decisions and for the presentation of automatic decisions (multi-layer environment, plot position indicator, intuitive, easy to use, that allows learning with experience, etc) [2]. The graphical operating environment is as important as the decision-making automatism for the success of a specific mission [1], [2], [3].

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE FOR CONTEXT ADAPTATION

Figure 1 shows an overview of the possible use cases of the MSCS (Maritime Surveillance and Control System), where it can be seen:

- Military operations and missions: coastal surveillance, borders control, special areas protection, prevention of illegal activities (piracy, drug trafficking, illegal immigration).
- Civil operations: search, rescue, and safety operations, environmental protection and pollution surveillance, fishing areas protection, support and assistance to military missions.

The Real System Architecture where MSCS has been deployed consists of:

- Coast surveillance system for the Ministry of Defence (Navy) of Cameroon.
- Seven (7) radar stations and two (2) control centres.
- Radar & AIS detection complemented with radio direction finders, electro optical and meteorological systems.

Figure 2 shows the general architecture for this analysis, focused on the best practices for the integration RADAR and AIS sensors and the best practices for decision making, as described in this paper, in order to enhance the local and system tracks results.

Fig. 2. General architecture for context adaptation

The contextual configuration represents all the geographic areas with associated parameters and algorithms, to be activated accordingly to the current state (with the necessary logic to guarantee seamless transitions during changes). Besides, the operator can modify on-line the active configuration considering for instance the quality metrics provided by the system. It features online configuration capabilities allowing to:

- Change the applied tracking/fusion algorithms.
- Modify the operating parameters of the running algorithms.
- Tune the characterization of the available sensors.

It also features zonal configuration capabilities allowing to:

- Apply these configurations to limited spatial regions and time spans in order to optimize the fusion integrity by area adjustments.
- Use powerful or more specific configurations for localized scenarios (risks, hazards, clutter, anomalous behaviours, navigation alerts) and account for exceptional situations that can affect sensors configurations, such as weather anomalies or targets typology that imply specific detection requirements in real time and their automatic adaptation tuning.

The tracking process has some custom built-in rules to make the final output stable and robust. In addition, all works are focused on the resolution of inconsistencies. Some of the rules applied to make the fusion stable are:

- Dominance of AIS MMSI codes for labelling the tracks. This applies even in the case of a transponder switched off and started again later: the track remembers the previously associated MMSI.
- Sensor prioritization according to zonal quality indicators. Discrepancies between sensors or fusion events are resolved taking into account the reliability of the involved measures.
- Limited memory of past actions to avoid cyclic switching behaviours.

Fig. 3. Intermittence and label exchange. Commitments to resolve.

In order to resolve some inconsistencies, the following commitments must be identified as the Figure 3 shows:

- Intermittence: a target is represented by different measurements over time. The local tracker mistakenly decides to remove a track from a target that still exists within range of the sensor. Later, new detections will create another track that represents the same target.
- Label exchange: two targets, A and B, are represented on the local tracker by tracks a and b respectively. At the same time, the targets intersect in such a way that the sensor detections are erroneously assigned to the tracks. This can cause the tracks to change their correspondence ($A \rightarrow b, B \rightarrow a$).

III. GENERAL APPROACH

A. Best Practices For The Integration Of Sensors

The integration of new sensors in maritime surveillance systems is a great challenge, and a great advance, in the adaptation and expansion of data fusion processes from each sensor with a context-aided fusion. The analysis of this adaptation will allow identifying and concluding the usefulness of these sensors related to existing surveillance systems (AIS, Coastal Radar, Radio Direction Finder, EOS, meteorological /hydrological system), and related to the new generation OTH Radar, Passive Radar, MIMO Radar, etc. (Figure 1), [10], [6], as well as the most suitable algorithms (PDA, JPDA, advanced Kalman, MHT, IMM) [1], [4], [8], [9].

The methodology for online configuration consists of the configuration of each tracking / fusion steps with the technique / algorithm to be applied, along with the desired parameter

values for redundant channels (master/slave processing). Figure 4 shows the Online HMI. Starting from this point, the implemented system allows to:

- Modify the value of any parameter. E.g.: change the N/M values of the deletion algorithm to improve behaviour on high-clutter conditions.
- Change any of the selected technique/algorithm. E.g.: Switch from Kalman filtering algorithm to an Interactive Multiple Model (IMM) filter, with the appropriate logic to do the hand-over between algorithms (state/covariance initialization and other parameters depending on each algorithm).

Fig. 4. Online fusion configuration HMI for AIS and Radar Sensors

Such events can take place at any time and are applied as soon as possible while guaranteeing the integrity of the data and processes.

B. Best Practices For Decision Making

The integration of new technologies such as advanced human-machine interface, navigation, communications and interoperability, automatic processing of sensor information, augmented cognition, modelling and simulation, imply the inclusion of new decision making processes. For example, the decision of the Risk Awareness Level [1], [2], [3], [5] (based on an analysis of a combination of tactical vessel alerts: Restricted Area Intrusion, Vessel Approaching Avoid, Vessel Collision Avoid, Course Not Allowed, Pollution or Dangerous Cargo, Outside Security Area, Fishing Intrusion, Possible Hostile Target, etc), or specific clutter conditions in an area. Thus, it will be very critical to identify these areas in order to optimize the context adaptation configuration and to enhance the Automatic Decision Making Mechanisms.

The methodology for zonal configuration of algorithms and parameters consists of the definition of regions with a different configuration (algorithms and parameters to be applied there). Figure 5 shows the Zonal HMI. Starting from this point, the implemented system allows to:

- Add a new spatial region that will have a different configuration.
- Remove existing regions or change their algorithms and parameters.

Fig. 5. Zonal fusion configuration HMI

C. Quality Metrics

One key aspect to evaluate the Quality of Service (QoS) of the context fusion adaptation is to make it generate operation metrics. With this metrics we will be able to evaluate the real-time performance of the data fusion system, as well as to provide some valuable information that can be useful while adjusting other parts of the architecture, like sensors, local trackers, fusion algorithms, or specific zones.

These metrics can be monitored in real-time for controlling that the output values are in a normal operation range. Abnormal parameters may let us know that there is some misconfiguration in the environment, like a sensor, or an algorithm parameter. Sudden changes may also be caused by a faulty sensor, so it can be useful also for reacting to unexpected events.

The most relevant metrics taken into account are: average filter residual, time between updates, number of integrity fails, number of recombination, number of total global tracks, number of global track creations, number of total erased global tracks, number of fused tracks, number of predicted tracks, average fused track distance.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Validating a context adaptation system can be somewhat similar to validating a software design. It is necessary to validate all possible situations, especially corner cases where the algorithms may fail or provide an unexpected behaviour. This can be partially achieved by using recorded datasets from a real environment. However, finding all corner cases in a real dataset can be very time consuming and sometimes all cases will not be correctly covered.

For this task, a scenario editor has been used to help in the task of designing surveillance environments for testing the algorithms. An ad-hoc tool has been developed in order to evaluate the configuration of some key aspects of the environment, like Radars and AIS stations, with some basic parameters like position, altitude, maximum range, azimuth-distance error, or period. In these environments it is also possible to design tracks trajectories by setting a set of waypoints with an associated speed, rate of turn, delays, and so on.

In addition, real recorded radar and AIS tracks from MSCS system [1], [2] are used to improve the context adaptation

response and to detect and identify the most critical scenarios conflicts and commitments.

The principal objective of this section is illustrating some system possibilities to improve the result in different situations. So the scenario's result with a default configuration will be shown and next, different tests will be performed with others algorithms or different values in the parameters, in order to compare the results.

As it can be seen in Figure 6 (the image above), the system generates the fused results with some errors. Most of the errors come from the upper track (Target 3), with some discontinuities due to bad association in one or more sensors. For instance, in Figure 6 (the image below), we can see the fused results without these errors.

Fig. 6. Solving the losses in the global track trajectories by online configuration.

Next some context adaptation cases are described:

- **Objective 1:** test lost targets with online algorithms. In this version of the scenario there are losses in the trajectories, in sensors 5 and 7. The loss of the two sensors is solved, thanks to adjusting the gating configuration to $N = 6$ instead of $N = 3$, so that these sensors no longer have trajectory losses (Fig. 6.- the image below) but, therefore, a commutation (label

exchange) occurs on the path of target 1 with the path of target 2 at sensor 7 (Fig. 7.- The image on the right).

To solve this problem on sensor 7, the configuration will be applied to it in a certain time frame in order to reduce losses and to avoid the switching caused in the trajectories of Targets 1 and 2.

Fig. 7. Solving local track commutation by online configuration. Sensor 7.

Figure 7 shows how, in the first two images where the default configuration is restored at the instant of time 700 and 800, it is possible to avoid switching in the trajectories of targets 1 and 2, but if it is restored at the instant 900 (later), switching is not avoided (Fig. 7-The image on the right).

- **Objective 2:** test manoeuvring targets in different areas with zonal algorithms.

The same scenario, for resolving by means of zonal configuration, has the need to define two zones since the losses occur at two different points in the scenario. In each of them, the configuration that is required can be applied. To resolve this situation, there are several options. One of these options is to set the gating parameter with a bigger size for association, now applying only zonal configuration. Figure 8 shows the zones that have been defined to apply the necessary configuration on the gating parameter.

Fig. 8. Scenario editor. Defined zones.

In this case, an event must be defined for each sensor and zone. For instance, Figure 9 shows the fused results without losses errors.

Another option is using a more advanced tracker like IMM algorithm (Interactive Multiple Model Filter). That algorithm will do a better adjustment based on target's manoeuvring models.

The possibility of changing the parameters depends on the area where targets are. This possibility allows specifying the best configuration for the different situations, without compromising the rest of the scenario.

Fig. 9. Solving the losses in the trajectories by zonal configuration.

Finally, in the Figure 10, the results with different algorithms can be compared. The same scenario simulation has been run 3 times: applying to the Kalman area with the biggest gating (red line), IMM1 (blue line), IMM2 (pink line). Target 3 enters the zone in 520 s. in the three simulations.

Fig. 10. Tracking errors with alternative filters (KALMAN; IMM1; IMM2)

Objective 3: test cell resolutions in different areas.

- Cells resolution depends on the distance to the radar and on its azimuth precision. This also affects to the tracks discrimination.
- There are areas in which the declared radar component (track) presents such a large error with respect to that declared by another radar that its contribution to the global track (fusion) worsens the measurement and tracking of the target. In these cases it can be decided in which areas that radar will contribute and in which ones it will not.

CONCLUSIONS

This context adaptation system must be conceived as something that will be working normally during long periods of time, mainly for providing the operator with stable tracks. So the system may need changes in its parameters or algorithms in order to satisfy new requirements, or environmental changes.

Therefore, as well as any other software, it should be able to be adaptable during its operation by allowing changing algorithms, parameters, defining contextual information, mask zones, and in general terms controlling every aspect of the fusion and context adaptation chain. This is also especially useful while tuning the fusion algorithms, as it is easy to change a parameter and observe in real-time the output in the screen. Changing parameters in real-time will affect also to the fusion metrics, so this feature can be combined with the fusion metrics to easily

tune the algorithms and receive feedback in real-time. This way it will be easy to adjust the parameters when running the data fusion system for the first time. In the same way, if fusion metrics report bad quality, it will be required to either check the source sensors or to adjust the algorithms for the new environment conditions.

The described system has been designed to provide with highly configurable sensor fusion logic, where the algorithms and parameters can be modified accordingly to predefined areas and also on-line from operator commands, taking care of smooth transitions in the changes of configuration.

Some simulated scenarios have been analysed to illustrate the capability to be adapted and solve typical tracking problems in representative situations. Additionally, real scenarios have been configured and improved, such as Figure 11 shows.

Fig. 11. Real scenario configured online and by area.[1]

Related to context exploitation:

- IMM filter improves behaviour in areas in cases of abrupt manoeuvres at high speed, although in scenarios with very accentuated manoeuvres in proximity of target crossings and low resolution, it cannot avoid switching.
- PDA / JPDA algorithms improve performance in high clutter and / or high noise areas, target tracking is more robust, there are fewer losses / divergences during filtering and less path fragmentation. However, it lacks robustness during runway initialization, especially with fast targets or widely spaced measurements.

The configuration of adaptation to the context requires a long observation time to detect all the anomalies produced by changes in the scenario (specific storms, variation of sea clutter, appearance of new fixed obstacles in the line of sight of the radar beam, deforestation, variations in the dynamics of the targets from one respect to another, etc.). This implies that observation must be made continuously to be able to optimize, with the appropriate mechanisms, the response of the system both at the global level and at the zonal level. Among the main observation tasks it is recommended to identify:

- Low precision areas (far areas): Identify areas in which a radar source produces a lot of uncertainty because its refresh period is high (few measurements)

and the target is very far from that source (greater error), compared to other sources that detect it.

- Ship crossing areas: Identify areas with possible shielding from one ship to another, as false recombinations could occur which should be avoided by being stricter in recombination.
- Areas of abrupt maneuvers: Identify areas where the prediction deviates from the primary detections. The prediction (kalman 0.3-0.45) could be trusted more in those sensors whose tracker response is very good (good fit) and whose systematic error is lower (nearby areas or radars with greater precision in their adjustment - short pulse, higher turning frequency, higher PRF, less range, etc.)
- Areas of high traffic density: Identify scenarios with many nearby targets in which, due to distance, an erroneous local association (local tracking) could be made between different measurements of plots to the same track (local label switching).

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